

Synthesis of 8-Substituted-10, 11-Dihydro-11-Oxo-5H-Dibenzo (b, e) (1, 4) Diazepines : Part II

RAMAN GROVER and B. C. JOSHI

Chemical Laboratories, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-4.

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Diazonium salt of 8-amino-10, 11-dihydro-11-oxo-5H-dibenzo (b, e) (1, 4) diazepine (1) was condensed with phenol, resorcinol α - and β -naphthols, 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic and 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids separately when azo dyes (2-7) were obtained. The structures of these azo dyes were established through elemental analysis and spectral studies. Colour reactions of these dyes have also been discussed.

DIBENZODIAZEPINES known as potent CNS drugs are used as antihistaminic, antiparkinson and neuroleptic drugs^{1,2}. Tarpan³, Noveril⁴, Clozapine⁵ are marketed drugs. Azo dyes are also important class of pharmacological drugs^{6,7}. It was, therefore, thought to synthesize azo-derivatives of 8-amino-10, 11-dihydro-11-oxo-5H-dibenzo(b, e) (1, 4) diazepine (1)⁸. Diazonium salt of 1 was condensed at 0-5° with phenol, resorcinol, α - and β -naphthols 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic and 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acids separately when corresponding azo dyes (2-7) with greenish yellow to orange shades were obtained.

Experimental

All the m. p.'s are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord using KBr pellets. The purity of the compounds was ascertained by tlc using silica gel-G as stationary phase and C₆H₆ : C₂H₅OH : NH₃ (7 : 2 : 1-solvent layer) as mobile phase.

1-Hydroxy-4-[8-Azo-10, 11-Dihydro-11-Oxo-5H-Dibenzo(b, e) (1, 4) Diazepinyl] Benzene (2) :

To a diazotised solution of 1 (1.1250 g, 0.005 M, in 3 ml of conc. HCl, 2 ml of CH₃COOH and 0.4 g of NaNO₂ at 0-5°) alkaline solution of phenol (0.47 g in 5 ml of 10% NaOH) was gradually added with stirring. The precipitated dye was crystallised from ethanol (2, m. p. 270° d ; yield 1.010 g, .003 M, Rf. 0.60).

Analysis :

Found : C, 69.35 ; H, 4.42 ; N, 16.68 per cent.
Calcd. for : C₁₉H₁₄O₂N₂ (2)
C, 69.09 ; H, 4.24 ; N, 16.97 per cent.

On similar lines, the diazotised solution of 1 was condensed with resorcinol, α -naphthol, β -naphthol, 1-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid and 3-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid separately when the compounds 3-7 were obtained. The results of elemental analyses, melting points and yields of these dyes are compiled in Table 1.

Discussion

Azo dyes (2-7) gave blue to violet colour in acids (2 and 4-blue and 3, 5, 6 and 7-violet). On basification the colour of acidic solution of these dyes changed (2-brown ; 3-yellow ; 4-red ; 5-red ; 6-orange ; 7-red). The characteristic colour of these dyes in H₂SO₄ did not disappear even on boiling, these dyes were greenish yellow to orange in solid state changing to yellow in alcoholic solution. However, the alcoholic solution of 5 was red in colour.

The experimental values of elemental analyses were in agreement with the theoretical values as shown in Table 1.

Spectral Studies :

The absorption spectra of 2-7 were obtained in DMF and their λ max values alongwith molar extinc-

TABLE-1

Compound Number	Molecular formula	Melting point	Yield %	Rf	Analysis %					
					Calculated			Found		
					C	H	N	C	H	N
2	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	270°d	60.0	0.60	69.09	4.24	16.97	69.35	4.42	16.68
3	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	279°d	57.80	0.72	65.90	4.05	16.18	65.55	4.55	16.38
4	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	301°d	60.00	0.62	72.63	4.21	14.74	72.96	3.98	14.54
5	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	291°d	68.16	0.54	72.63	4.21	14.74	72.98	3.90	14.56
6	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	305°d	56.60	0.68	67.92	3.77	15.09	67.56	3.98	15.29
7	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	309°d	57.55	0.64	67.92	3.77	15.09	67.58	4.02	15.33

TABLE-2

Compound Number	Visible region		Infra-red region	Colour in Acid Medium	Colour in Alkaline Medium
	max cm^{-1}	ϵ	Characteristic Absorption bonds cm^{-1}		
2	412	12000	3565, 1640, 1580, 1405	Blue	Brown
3	455	12300	3565, 1650, 1575, 1395	Violet	Yellow
4	430	12065	3560, 1650, 1585, 1405	Blue	Red
5	475	13076	3560, 1645, 1575, 1380	Violet	Red
6	428	11904	3540, 1660, 1630, 1580		
7	425	12698	1395, 990, 1265 . .	Violet	Orange
			3540, 1660, 1635, 1580, 1395, 1260, 985	Violet	Red

tion coefficient have been given in Table 2. These compounds were found to obey Beer's law.

Visible Absorption Spectra :

The absorption in the visible range was also studied. The values of λ_{max} were found in the range 475-412 cm^{-1} . In the study of maximum absorption in visible range and visible colours, the range for compounds 2, 4, 6 and 7 which were yellow with greenish tinge was 430-400 cm^{-1} . λ_{max} for 3 and 5 which were yellow with a little orange tinge were 455 cm^{-1} and 475 cm^{-1} respectively. The suggested range for such dyes (like 2 and 5) is 490-430 cm^{-1} .

Infra-red Spectra :

The ir spectra of 1-7 were recorded in KBr pellets and were compared.

Although the ir spectra in the range of 1600-1100 cm^{-1} were quite complicated due to the presence of various groups and aromatic system but the absorption peaks in the vicinity of 1575 cm^{-1} and 1395 cm^{-1} appearing as side bands in the ir spectra of 2-7 were absent in the ir spectrum of 1 and these could be assigned to $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ stretching in these compounds. Strong absorption bands at 1660 cm^{-1} present in the ir spectra of 6 and 7 were absent in those of 1-5. The absorption bands also appeared in the vicinity of 1260 cm^{-1} and 940-930 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of 6 and 7 only. All these could be attributed to the presence of carboxyl group in 6 and 7.

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